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ASSESSING THE SATISFACTION OF DOMESTIC TOURISTS WITH COMMUNITY-BASED TOURISM DESTINATIONS: A CASE STUDY OF THANH TOAN TILE-ROOFED BRIDGE IN THUA THIEN HUE PROVINCE, VIETNAM

Abstract. This paper aims to evaluate the satisfaction of domestic tourists participating in community-based tourism (CBT) at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thua Thien Hue province, Vietnam. The research data was collected directly from 157 domestic tourists through a questionnaire at the Thanh Toan Bridge destination. The study utilized descriptive statistics to answer the research questions. Domestic tourist satisfaction was measured and evaluated based on six factors: (1) Tourism resources; (2) Infrastructure; (3) Tourist environment; (4) Security and safety; (5) Local residents; and (6) Service prices. Based on the research results, the author proposed several solutions to improve the satisfaction of domestic tourists at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge.

Keywords: Community-Based Tourism (CBT), satisfaction, domestic tourists, Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, Thua Thien Hue province, Vietnam

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ОЦЕНКА УДОВЛЕТВОРЕННОСТИ ВНУТРЕННИХ ТУРИСТОВ ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫМИ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯМИ: ПРИМЕР МОСТА С ЧЕРЕПИЧНОЙ КРЫШЕЙ ТХАНЬ ТОАН В ПРОВИНЦИИ ТХУА ТХИЕН ХЮЭ, ВЬЕТНАМ

Целью статьи является оценка удовлетворённости местных туристов, участвующих в общественном туризме на мосту Тхань Тоан с черепичной крышей в провинции Тхуа Тхиен Хюэ, Вьетнам. Данные исследования были собраны непосредственно у 157 местных туристов с помощью анкеты в пункте назначения у моста Тхань Тоан. В исследовании использовалась описательная статистика для ответа на исследовательские вопросы. Удовлетворённость внутреннего туризма измерялась и оценивалась на основе шести факторов: (1) туристические ресурсы; (2) инфраструктура; (3) туристическая среда; (4) охрана и безопасность; (5) местные жители; и (6) цены на услуги. На основе результатов исследования автор предложил несколько решений по повышению удовлетворённости внутренних туристов на мосту с черепичной крышей Тхань Тоан.

Ключевые слова: *общественный туризм, удовлетворение, внутренние туристы, Мост с черепичной крышей Тхань Тоан, провинция Тхуа Тхиен Хюэ, Вьетнам*

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1. Introduction

Currently, community tourism is considered the type of tourism that brings the most sustainable economic development benefits to indigenous communities. This type of tourism not only helps to protect ecological resources, but also preserves and promotes unique local cultural features [20].

Thua Thien Hue, a province in Vietnam, has great potential for developing community-based tourism due to its rich traditional cultural heritage in the ancient capital, rural areas, and upland regions inhabited by ethnic minorities [21]. In Thua Thien Hue province, several localities have strongly developed forms of organizing community tourism, such as the Phuoc Tich ancient village in Phong Dien district, Suoi Voi tourist area in Phu Loc district, Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thuy Thanh commune, Huyen Tran Cultural Center, and An Tay Ward in Hue city [13].

Huong Thuy town, located in Thua Thien Hue province, is currently focusing its resources on stimulating demand and developing community tourism. One particular area, Thuy Thanh commune, has the potential to become a thriving community tourism destination due to its five historical relics, three of which are nationally recognized and two are provincially recognized [16]. Among these five relics, the Tile-Roofed Bridge stands out as a top destination for local community tourism, having been officially recognized as such by the People's Committee of Thua Thien Hue province in 2019. This bridge not only holds great value in Vietnam's development, but also serves as a renowned symbol of the country's rich architectural heritage. Through the Hue Festivals, experiential services, and community tourism programs at the Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge area have attracted a significant number of domestic and international tourists. However, despite over a decade of development, community tourism at the Tile-Roofed Bridge still requires direction and solutions to better cater to the needs of tourists.

Therefore, this study analyzed and evaluated the satisfaction of domestic tourists

participating in community-based tourism at Thanh Toan Bridge. Based on this analysis, the article proposed specific measures to improve the satisfaction of domestic tourists at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge.

2. Literature review

Community-based tourism (CBT)

"Community-based tourism" is a term that has been mentioned around the world since the 70s of the 20th century [3; 11; 22]. However, there are various interpretations of this concept among researchers. For instance, The Mountain Institute [18] defines CBT as a mutually meaningful interaction between hosts and visitors, resulting in economic benefits for local communities and the environment. Goodwin and Santilli [2] view CBT as tourism activities that are owned or managed by the community in order to generate greater benefits for the community. Hausler and Strasdas [5] suggest that, "community tourism involves the active involvement of local people in the development and management process, leading to economic benefits for the local economy". The World Wide Fund for Nature defines "CBT as a form of tourism where the local community has ownership and participation in the development and management process, with most of the benefits being returned to the community" [17].

Tourist satisfaction

The concept of tourist satisfaction originated from the concept of customer satisfaction. In recent years, numerous scientific researchers around the world have conducted studies on customer satisfaction and evaluating tourist satisfaction. Based on the theoretical basis of customer satisfaction, many studies evaluating tourists' satisfaction with a destination have appeared, for example, Hughes, 1991; Kozak and Rimmington, 2000; Truong and King, 2009; Chen., Zhang., and Qiu, 2013; Puh, 2014; Hossain, 2020; Morshed., Hashim., and Mahmood, 2022.

Factors to evaluate tourist satisfaction with a community tourism destination will be different depending on each destination. Omotoba et al. [14] evaluated the level of tourist's satisfaction with CBT for sustainability in Ekiti State, Nigeria

based on sustainable development indicators such as economic, infrastructural, socio-cultural, and environmental factors. In 2022, a study by Lan and Truc [9] evaluated tourists' satisfaction with community tourism in My Hoa Hung, Vietnam based on five factors: environmental landscapes; infrastructure; security-safety; human; infrastructure; and prices. Among these five factors, the human factor was rated the most satisfied and the security and safety factor was rated the lowest in terms of satisfaction by tourists. In 2024, Chung Le Khang and colleagues [10] examined factors affecting the satisfaction of domestic tourists participating in CBT at Thieng Lieng Island. The study evaluated the satisfaction of tourists based on seven factors: natural resources, infrastructure, tourist environment, service quality, local

residents' attitudes, pricing of services, and cultural heritage.

3. Research methodology

This article utilized both qualitative and quantitative research methods to examine tourists' satisfaction with a specific tourist destination, specifically a CBT destination. The author conducted a thorough review of existing scientific articles on the topic and also developed a questionnaire using quantitative research methods. The sample was selected through convenience sampling.

To evaluate tourists' satisfaction with CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, the questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale where 1 = very dissatisfied; 2 = dissatisfied; 3 = neutral; 4 = satisfied; and 5 = very satisfied, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Questionnaire for evaluating domestic tourists' Satisfaction

Factors		Levels of satisfaction				
Factor I: Tourism resources at the destination (TR)		Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
TR1	Beautiful, peaceful scenery	1	2	3	4	5
TR2	The historical relic "Thanh Toan tile bridge" is unique	1	2	3	4	5
TR3	Attractive traditional craft villages (Cham non craft, Dan lat craft, and fishing craft)	1	2	3	4	5
TR4	Attractive local traditional arts (Bai choi festival, Ho gia gao, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5
TR5	Diversity of local cuisine	1	2	3	4	5
Factor II: Infrastructure (IN)		Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
IN1	Convenience means of transport and transportation system to the tourist destination	1	2	3	4	5
IN2	Spacious parking area at the community tourism destination	1	2	3	4	5
IN3	The cleanliness and complete amenities of the restroom	1	2	3	4	5
IN4	Adequate electricity and water supply	1	2	3	4	5
IN5	Good health care system	1	2	3	4	5
Factor III: Tourist environment (TE)		Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
TE1	Clean and unpolluted	1	2	3	4	5
TE2	Fresh, cool air	1	2	3	4	5
TE3	Beautiful landscape decoration	1	2	3	4	5
TE4	Policies to ensure environmental hygiene	1	2	3	4	5
Factor IV: Security and safety (SS)		Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
SS1	Security at community-based tourism destinations (No situations such as robbery, racketeering, price gouging, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5
SS2	Traffic safety	1	2	3	4	5

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Levels of satisfaction</i>				
SS3 Food safety and hygiene	1	2	3	4	5
Factor V: Local residents (LR)	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
LR1 Friendly, polite and enthusiastic	1	2	3	4	5
LR2 Ready to support and respond to tourists' requests	1	2	3	4	5
LR3 Have good knowledge about tourism	1	2	3	4	5
LR4 Have knowledge of local culture and history	1	2	3	4	5
Factor VI: Service Prices (PR)	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
PR1 Food and beverage service prices	1	2	3	4	5
PR2 Prices of accommodation services	1	2	3	4	5
PR3 Prices of sightseeing and experience	1	2	3	4	5
PR4 Prices for souvenirs and local products	1	2	3	4	5
PR5 Entertainment prices	1	2	3	4	5

The meaning of each average value for the 5-point Likert scale is as follows: Level 1 ranges from 1.00 to 1.80 (Very dissatisfied); Level 2 ranges from 1.81 to 2.60 (Dissatisfied); Level 3 ranges from 2.61 to 3.40 (Neutral); Level 4 ranges from 3.41 to 4.20 (Satisfied); and Level 5 ranges from 4.21 to 5.00 (Very satisfied). The distance value is calculated by subtracting the minimum value from the maximum value and dividing by the total number of values (n), which in this case is 5. Therefore, the distance value is $(5 - 1)/5 = 0.8$.

According to Hair et al. [6], the minimum sample size for research should be at least five times the total number of observed variables. In this study, 26 variables were measured, meaning that the minimum sample size should have been $26 \times 5 = 130$ samples. However, the study used a survey of 160 domestic tourists to evaluate their satisfaction with CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thua Thien Hue province. The data collected from the survey was then processed and analyzed using the statistical software SPSS 22.0.

4. Results and discussions

To assess the satisfaction of domestic tourists participating in CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, we conducted a survey of 160 respondents at the destination. Out of the total survey responses, 157 were deemed valid. The data was then analyzed using SPSS 22.0 software. The characteristics of the study sample are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2 – Characteristics of research sample

		<i>Number of respondents (N)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Gender	Male	72	45.9
	Female	85	54.1
Age	Under 18	8	5.1
	18 – 25	40	25.5
	26 – 35	72	45.9
	36 – 50	23	14.6
	Above 50	14	8.9
Occupation	Student	32	20.4
	Businessman	39	24.8
	Civil servants and state employees	24	15.3
	General Laborer	55	35.0
	Retired person	7	4.5
Number of visits	First time	80	51.0
	Two times	56	35.7
	Three times	14	8.9
	More than three-times	7	4.5

The results of the survey indicate that the majority of respondents were female (54.1%), while the remaining 45.9% were male. The age distribution of the 157 participants was as follows: under 18 years of age (5.1%), between 18 – 25 years of age (25.5%), between 26 – 35 years of age (45.9%), between 36 – 50 years of age (14.6%), and above 50 years of age (8.9%). The occupations of the surveyed individuals were not evenly distributed, with the highest proportion (35.0%) being general laborers. Other

occupations, such as businessmen (24.8%), students (20.4%), and civil servants and state employees (15.3%), also accounted for a significant portion of the respondents. Retired individuals made up the smallest proportion at 4.5%. In terms of the frequency of visits to Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, 51.0% of tourists were visiting for the first time, 35.7% had visited twice, 8.9% had visited three times, and only 4.5% had visited more than three times.

Table 3 – Satisfaction level of domestic tourists at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

Factors	Number of respondents (N)					Mean	Std. Deviation	Evaluation
	1	2	3	4	5			
Factor I: Tourism resources at the destination (Average = 4.03)								
TR1	0	0	8	118	31	4.15	±0.48	Satisfied
TR2	0	0	0	79	78	4.50	±0.50	Very satisfied
TR3	0	16	8	85	48	4.05	±0.88	Satisfied
TR4	0	8	16	85	48	4.10	±0.78	Satisfied
TR5	0	16	86	39	16	3.35	±0.80	Neutral
Factor II: Infrastructure (Average = 3.46)								
IN1	0	0	32	93	32	4.00	±0.64	Satisfied
IN2	0	16	87	46	8	3.29	±0.72	Neutral
IN3	8	24	72	53	0	3.08	±0.83	Neutral
IN4	0	0	40	102	15	3.84	±0.57	Satisfied
IN5	0	24	94	39	0	3.10	±0.63	Neutral
Factor III: Tourist environment (Average = 3.60)								
TE1	0	16	94	47	0	3.20	±0.60	Neutral
TE2	0	0	39	94	24	3.90	±0.63	Satisfied
TE3	0	0	24	109	24	4.00	±0.55	Satisfied
TE4	0	0	117	32	8	3.31	±0.56	Neutral
Factor IV: Security and safety (Average = 3.63)								
SS1	8	32	85	24	8	2.95	±0.88	Neutral
SS2	0	0	32	87	38	4.04	±0.67	Satisfied
SS3	0	0	40	94	23	3.89	±0.63	Satisfied
Factor V: Local residents (Average = 3.92)								
LR1	0	0	16	102	39	4.15	±0.58	Satisfied
LR2	0	0	31	86	40	4.06	±0.67	Satisfied
LR3	0	16	86	39	16	3.35	±0.80	Neutral
LR4	0	0	23	94	40	4.11	±0.63	Satisfied
Factor VI: Service Prices (Average = 3.94)								
PR1	0	0	31	94	32	4.01	±0.64	Satisfied
PR2	0	0	47	94	16	3.80	±0.60	Satisfied
PR3	0	7	8	95	47	4.16	±0.71	Satisfied
PR4	0	0	63	78	16	3.70	±0.65	Satisfied
PR5	0	8	16	94	39	4.04	±0.75	Satisfied

The results in Table 3 indicate that, overall, domestic tourists were highly satisfied with all six factors, with an average rating ranging from 3.46 to 4.03. However, there were variations in how tourists evaluated the criteria within each factor, with ratings ranging from very dissatisfied to very satisfied. The satisfaction levels for each criteria within the factors are as follows:

Tourism resources at the destination

The highest rated factor among domestic tourists was "tourism resources", with an average score of 4.03. While there were differences in the observed variables within each factor, they were not significant. The variable TR2 received a very satisfied rating with an average score of 4.50. TR1, TR3, and TR4 were rated as quite satisfied, while TR5 received a neutral rating from domestic tourists. This assessment is reasonable due to the Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge being a national architectural and artistic relic, known for its uniqueness and ancient history. Located on the outskirts of Hue City, the bridge offers a beautiful and natural countryside landscape, making it an ideal destination for community tourism activities. Besides, this destination has many traditional craft villages and offers a variety of attractive and long-standing local traditional arts. However, the criterion "diversity of local cuisine" received a neutral rating from tourists. This suggests that there has not been enough investment in promoting and developing local cuisine compared to the diverse and rich cuisine of Hue.

Infrastructure

The infrastructure at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge destination was rated relatively well by tourists, with an average score of 3.46. However, it was the lowest-rated factor among the six factors evaluated. Of the five variables related to infrastructure, two variables (IN1 and IN4) received the highest ratings with average values of 4.00 and 3.84 respectively, indicating a high level of satisfaction. The remaining three variables (IN2, IN3, and IN5) were rated at a neutral level. This is likely due to the convenient transportation system in the area, as the destination is located near Hue city center. Additionally, the

electricity and water systems at the destination are consistently reliable. However, there are some limitations in terms of infrastructure. For example, the current parking area at the community tourism destination is not spacious enough to accommodate large vehicles for tourist groups. The toilet facilities also do not provide enough space and comfort for visitors, and there is a fee for using them. These limitations may contribute to lower satisfaction ratings among tourists.

Tourist environment

The tourism environment at Tile-Roofed Bridge destination received a positive rating from domestic tourists, with an average score of 3.46. The variables TE3 and TE2 received the highest ratings, with average scores of 4.00 and 3.90 respectively, indicating a satisfactory level. The Thanh Toan bridge destination is situated in a rural area with abundant trees, providing fresh and cool air. Additionally, it is a well-known community tourism spot, resulting in the surrounding landscape being beautifully adorned with vibrant colors. However, the remaining variables, TE1 and TE4, received neutral ratings from tourists, with average scores of 3.2 and 3.31 respectively. This suggests that during community tourism events at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, there is still a problem with littering, leading to environmental pollution. Furthermore, tourists do not have a clear understanding of the local authorities' policies regarding environmental hygiene at community tourism destinations.

Security and safety

Among the three variables related to safety and security, SS2 received the highest rating of 4.04, indicating a high level of satisfaction. SS3 received a satisfaction rating of 3.80, while the lowest rated variable was SS1 with a neutral rating of 2.95. The Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge is a well-known community tourism destination, and as such, ensuring traffic safety is always a top

priority during community tourism activities. Additionally, the local people guarantee the safety and hygiene of the dishes served. However, there have been instances where tourists have felt pressured or coerced into purchasing products during community tourism activities, leading to a decrease in overall satisfaction.

Local residents

One of the key factors in attracting tourists to community tourism destinations is the local people. In Thanh Toan village, the local people are highly appreciated by tourists, with an average rating of 3.92. Out of the four variables related to the "local people" factor, three were rated with high levels of satisfaction by tourists: LR1, LR2, and LR4. Among these three variables, LR1 received the highest rating of 4.15. According to reviews from tourists, the local people are known for their friendliness, supportiveness, and responsiveness to tourists' needs. They are also knowledgeable about the culture and history of the Thanh Toan Bridge destination. However, the variable LR3 received a lower rating of 3.35, indicating that tourists are not completely satisfied with the level of tourism knowledge among the local people.

Service Prices

All five variables (PR1, PR2, PR3, PR4, and PR5) in the "service prices" factor received high satisfaction ratings from domestic tourists. Specifically, variable PR3 received the highest average rating of 4.16, while variable PR4 received the lowest average rating of 3.70. This indicates that the prices for dining, accommodation, sightseeing experiences, and other services at the community tourism destination were deemed suitable for tourists.

Based on the analysis of research results, we proposed several key solutions to enhance the satisfaction of domestic tourists when participating in CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge (Table 4).

Table 4 – Solutions to enhance the satisfaction of domestic tourists at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

No	Solutions
1.	Offering a variety of local cuisine
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local cuisine helps tourists recognize the unique cultural values of each region. Therefore, on occasions when community tourism activities take place at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, in addition to providing local dishes in Thanh Toan village, we should also include dishes with traditional features of Hue cuisine, such as clam rice; Hue beef noodle soup; Loc cake; Nam cake; Hue sweet soup.
2.	Improving infrastructure
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The local authorities should prioritize investing in expanding the parking area at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, a popular community tourism destination. This includes building more parking lots to accommodate large vehicles for group tours. – The restroom facilities at the bridge are not only essential for tourists, but also play a crucial role in promoting urban development. Therefore, it is imperative for the authorities to invest in building and expanding the toilet system at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge. This should also include equipping the restroom with modern amenities such as hand sanitizer systems and automatic drying machines to cater to the needs of tourists. – There is a need to enhance and improve the overall health care system in the area.
3.	Ensuring cleanliness of the tourist environment
	<p>During community tourism events at Thanh Toan Bridge, there is often environmental pollution, particularly during the Hue Festival and Tet. To maintain cleanliness at the destination, several solutions should be implemented, including:</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increasing the number of trash cans, posting signs prohibiting littering, and regularly broadcasting reminders through loudspeakers to tourists and locals. – Conducting training sessions to educate and raise awareness among local residents about the importance of maintaining environmental hygiene during festivals and the Lunar New Year at Thanh Toan Bridge. – Enforcing strict penalties for any violations that result in environmental pollution at community tourism destinations by local authorities.
4.	Ensuring safety and security
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local authorities should strengthen security forces to inspect and monitor to ensure the security of community tourism destinations. – Local authorities should consistently inspect, detect, prevent, and resolutely handle acts that disrupt security and safety at destinations such as robbery, price manipulation, etc.
5.	Enhancing the knowledge of local residents about tourism
	<p>Local people play a crucial role in CBT activities. In order to meet the needs of tourists, they must have a good understanding of tourism. To achieve this, the following solutions should be implemented:</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local authorities should regularly organize training classes to improve local people's knowledge and skills in serving tourists. – Local authorities should provide handbooks to local people on how to interact with tourists and promote local culture in CBT.

5. Conclusions

The study developed six factors for evaluating the satisfaction of domestic tourists participating in CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thua Thien Hue province. These factors include tourism resources, infrastructure, tourist environment, security and safety, local residents, and service prices. However, the research results indicate that many criteria within these factors do not meet

the expectations of Vietnamese tourists.

As a result, we proposed several solutions to enhance the satisfaction of domestic tourists at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge. These solutions include: (1) Offering a variety of local cuisine; (2) Improving infrastructure; (3) Ensuring cleanliness of the tourist environment; (4) Ensuring safety and security; and (5) Enhancing the knowledge of local residents about tourism.

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